

PARADISEC PODCAST SERIES, TOKSAVE: CULTURE TALKS

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Abstract

The podcast series 'Toksava: Culture Talks' was launched in 2019 by PARADISEC (the Pacific And Regional Archive for Digital Sources in Endangered Cultures) as an outreach project into new collaborative research to bridging the archives, communities and researchers. It is a series of interviews with people who have cultural and personal connections held in the archive. Music and language are central to identity to Indigenous communities and return of legacy research recordings can be an emotional and exciting rediscovery of the past, contributing to the continuation of cultural practices. The value of the podcast series as a research output enables the voices of Indigenous communities to be heard. Engaging community members through podcasting also increases accessibility and findability through the reuse of archival recordings to new recordings and knowledge with historical and cultural sensibilities. The PARADISEC podcast series is an example of recognizing the importance of communities and collaboration of its interdisciplinary work in digital preservation connecting archives, communities and researchers.

Keywords - Indigenous, culture, collaboration, connections, communities.

Conference Topics - Tūhono - Connect.

I. INTRODUCTION

In 2019, Jodie Kell and Steven Gagau embarked upon a project to produce a podcast based on the collections held in the PARADISEC archive. PARADISEC (the Pacific and Regional Archive for Digital Sources in Endangered Cultures) is a digital archive of records of some of the many small cultures and languages of the world accessible through an online catalogue. Using Kell's skills as an audio engineer and musicologist and Gagau's position as a community member based within the archive, in November 2019 they launched the podcast 'Toksava: Culture Talks', a series of interviews with people who have personal and cultural connections with the archive.

This poster presentation explores how the process of producing the podcast has not only generated new knowledge through metadata enhancement but has used contemporary technology to share and reshape archival collections through engagement with Indigenous community members. It demonstrates how the podcast production has value as a research output which recognizes the value of Indigenous knowledge systems and knowledge keepers (Kell & Gagau, 2020).

II. CONNECTION AND COLLABORATION

The importance of re-connecting Indigenous communities with heritage objects is a major factor in current archival practice and is central to discussions regarding accessibility (Harris et al. 2019, 138). Formed in 2003, PARADISEC aims to provide access to archival media recordings of endangered cultural groups. Rather than hold material objects, PARADISEC creates digital records of archival items, audio and video recordings, images and text. This ensures the longevity in digital form of often fragile obsolescent media such as reel to reel or cassette tapes. In its practice, PARADISEC aims not only to digitize and hold the materials into the future but also promote reconnection to communities by taking advantage of new technologies including its online catalogue.

The collaboration with communities such as the PNG Peroveta Singers of Canberra is a practical example of the PARADISEC 'archival loop' model used in community outreach, fostering cultural engagement between speaker communities and the archive. Working in the archive from an 'insider-outsider' perspective, Steven Gagau, a Tolai man believes this approach ensures cultural safety, accountability and value adding of archival materials from the past to the present. The Archival Loop focuses on:

- Empowering Indigenous voices – Valuing Indigenous people as experts and recognizing them as custodians of their own cultural knowledge.
- Connection and Reconnection – making archival materials accessible to enable the knowledge and lived experiences of cultural practices.
- Building Relationships – Prioritizing respectful intercultural relationships to ensure cultural safety, accountability and value for long term impact.
- Enlivening the Archive a- Bridging archives, communities and researchers inspires storytelling and song, cultural revitalization and the transmission of intergenerational knowledge.

III. CONCLUSION

The workflow of the podcast production developed by Kell and Gagau allows for Indigenous voices to be valued. Central to this is the importance of establishing relationships that ensure cultural safety. Co-producer Gagau has a unique position in that he is an Indigenous community member in the role of an archivist. Connecting and collaborating with community members throughout the podcast workflow, makes Gagau feel more in control of the research output. With new technologies and a new approach to research outputs, the podcast as a product and as a processual engagement with Indigenous communities contributes to unlocking the archives and opening up access to ethnographic collections.

REFERENCES (HEADING 4)

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AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Jodie Kell is Senior Research Officer and audio engineer at PARADISEC, University of Sydney. Her duties include Sydney office and projects management, archival operations supervision dealing with institutions, researchers and community members. Jodie is a co-producer of PARADISEC's podcast series, Toksave: Culture Talks as part of the community outreach program.

Steven Gagau is a cultural consultant and archivist at PARADISEC, University of Sydney. His duties include interdisciplinary research, archival collections metadata enrichment and community collaborations. Steven, an Indigenous Tolai man from PNG is also the co-producer of PARADISEC's podcast series, "Toksava: Culture Talks" as part of the community outreach program.

